

All plots received 60-10.6-32 kg NPK/ha (urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash).

Correlations were significant between seedling vigor and tiller number at maximum tillering (0.72** and between tiller number and vigor index (0.45*) (see table). Correlations also were significant between seedling vigor and grain yield (0.68**) and vigor index and grain yield (0.48*).

The results suggest genotype interactions with seed rate and with method of sowing. Fertilizer response was uniform.

The performance of transplanted rice in inland valley swamps may be influenced by the interaction of variety, method of sowing, and fertilization and of sowing, seed rate, and fertilization. Yield differences could be related more to variety than to duration or method of sowing. ■

Effect of nursery management techniques on grain yield of some released rice varieties in an inland valley swamp, Sierra Leone, 1988 wet season.

Fertilization	Sowing method	Grain yield (t/ha)						Sowing method	Fertilization
		ROK11		ROK5		ROK10			
		40 g seed/m ²	60 g seed/m ²	40 g seed/m ²	60 g seed/m ²	40 g seed/m ²	60 g seed/m ²		
Without NPK	Row	1.6	1.6	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.4	1.7	1.7
	Random	1.8	1.3	1.9	1.7	1.7	2.0	1.7	
With 40-40-40 kg NPK/ha	Row	2.0	1.9	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.0	2.1	2.1
	Random	1.8	1.7	2.2	2.4	1.9	2.2	2.0	
	Seed rate (mean)	1.8	1.6	2.1	2.1	1.9	1.9		
	Variety (mean)	1.7		2.1		1.9			
	Coefficient of variation							7.2%	
	LSD ^a (P=0.05)	Variety (V)						0.1	
		Seed rate (D)						ns	
		Method of sowing (S)						ns	
		Fertilization (F)						0.1	
		V*D						0.1	
		V*S						0.1	
		V*D*S						0.1	
		V*S*F						0.1	

^a ns = not significant.

Effect of plant spacing on ratoon rice performance

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We studied the effect of three plant spacings on ratooning ability of medium-duration varieties Ponni and Bhavani, in a factorial randomized block design. The crop was transplanted 21 Sep 1986 in sandy clay loam soil fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

The main crop was harvested 110 d after transplanting, leaving 15 cm stubble. Soil between rows was trampled to control weeds and to prune older roots. The ratoon crop was irrigated at 5 cm depth. Harvest was 67 d after ratooning.

Bhavani was significantly superior in growth, yield attributes, and yield in both main and ratoon crops (see table). Spacing significantly affected yield of the main crop but had no significant influence on ratoon yield. However, productive ratoon tillers/m² and ratoon dry matter production were significantly higher with close spacing.

The correlation of plant density with ratoon yield was positive and significant (see figure). ■

Effect of plant spacing on main (M) and ratoon (R) rice crops in Madurai, India.

	Productive tillers (no.)		Dry matter (t/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	M	R	M	R	M	R	M	R
<i>Variety</i>								
Ponni	445	319	10.0	7.2	4.7	1.8	5.6	2.3
Bhavani	469	414	10.7	7.3	5.5	2.8	6.2	3.4
LSD (0.05)	17	10	0.2	0.0	0.02	0.3	0.2	0.3
<i>Spacing</i>								
15* 10 cm	479	407	10.7	7.8	5.2	2.4	6.3	3.0
20* 10 cm	451	363	10.4	7.0	5.0	2.2	5.8	2.8
25* 10 cm	440	330	9.9	6.8	5.0	2.1	5.6	2.7
LSD ^a (0.05)	20	12	0.2	0.1	0.02	ns	0.2	ns

^a ns = nonsignificant.

Relationship between population density and ratoon grain yield. Madurai, India, 1986 wet season.

Effect of seedlings/hill on individual rice plant yield and yield components

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We studied the effects of seedlings/hill in medium-duration, second season irrigated rice variety E Wan 5 in Jul-Oct 1989. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 1-5 seedlings/hill, with 40 seedlings/treatment. Ten hills in the middle of each row were sampled to measure individual plant yield and yield components.

Rate of seed set appears to be the most stable yield component, followed by 1,000-grain weight, plant height, panicle

length, and harvest index (see table). The most unstable traits are grain yield/plant, total weight/plant, and panicle/plant.

Two or three seedlings/hill appears to yield best. ■

Effect of seedlings/hill on plant yield and yield components. Wuhan, China, 1989.

Seedlings/hill (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Panicles/plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)		Seed-set rate (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield/hill (g)	Grain yield/plant (g)	Grain weight/hill (g)	Grain weight/plant (g)	Harvest index
					Fertile	Total							
1	79.0	5.0	5.0	18.0	74.6	83.4	89.4	24.3	9.2	9.2	15.6	15.6	0.5
2	82.2	5.6	2.8	18.7	72.7	81.3	89.4	24.4	9.9	5.0	15.6	7.8	0.5
3	81.8	7.4	2.5	17.4	74.1	82.2	90.1	23.5	12.9	4.3	21.8	7.3	0.5
4	80.4	9.0	2.3	17.0	61.5	69.9	88.0	23.7	13.0	3.2	23.4	5.8	0.4
5	84.4	10.4	2.1	17.3	58.0	66.0	87.8	23.5	14.1	2.8	26.2	5.2	0.4
Mean	81.6	7.5	2.9	17.7	68.2	76.6	89.0	23.9	11.8	4.9	20.5	8.4	0.5
CV (%)	2.5	30.4	40.1	3.7	11.5	10.5	1.1	1.8	18.2	51.6	23.2	50.1	5.5

Integrated pest management — diseases

Status of rice blast (BI) in eastern Uttar Pradesh, India

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Rice is primarily grown as a hot-wet season (1 Jun-30 Nov) crop in eastern UP. Before the introduction of TN1, IR8, Jaya, and other high-yielding varieties, BI affected extensive rainfed rice areas. With the introduction of modern varieties, the area under irrigation increased. Varietal resistance and less frequent moisture stress reduced early and severe BI attack. With the consequent reduction in inoculum load and discontinued use of susceptible varieties, the area affected by BI shrank considerably.

By mid-1970s, BI had been confined to the submountain regions of Gonda, Bahraich, Basti, and Gorakhpur districts, (the eastern tarai). There, nearness to inoculum from Nepal and much more frequent cultivation of susceptible traditional rainfed varieties made it possible for the disease to recur each year.

The disease starts at the seedling stage (May) and eventually covers leaves, sheaths, nodes, panicle stalk, panicle node, and panicle proper. In years with several drought stress periods of 10 d or more, rainfed rice becomes uneconomic to harvest.

Our surveys of farmers' fields and experimental plots 1977-89 indicate BI incidence in the eastern plains as well. Jarhan seedlings raised under rainfed conditions at Faizabad are infected by Jul and, in years with even short droughts, are defoliated by mid-August. Under irrigation, foliar BI pressure remains low even on varieties that are susceptible when grown under rainfed conditions.

Neck BI is common to all ecosystems, both in the tarai and in the eastern plains. With the introduction of neck BI-susceptible varieties, it has become a serious problem. BI is increasing in extent and intensity with the increase of the area under better fertility. ■

Distribution of bacterial blight (BB) in Nepal

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We surveyed 32 rice-growing districts in the Terai and important rice-growing districts in the hills to map the distribution of BB disease. Areas inspected were mostly along the national highways. Disease incidence was calculated on a 1-m² area at each site as number of infected leaves/hill × 100.

Table 1. Distribution of BB in Nepal, 1986-89.

District	Sites surveyed (no.)	Average field infection (%)
Jhapa	5	>50
Morang	4	>50
Sunsari	3	10-25
Dhankuta	2	10-25
Saptari	3	26-50
Dhanusa	7	10-25
Siraha	6	10-25
Mahotari	6	10-25
Sarlahi	5	26-50
Rautahat	2	10-25
Bara	13	>50
Parsa	15	>50
Chitwan	6	10-25
Nawalparasi	4	10-25
Rupandehi	7	26-50
Kapilvastu	4	10-25
Dang	8	26-50
Banke	5	10-25
Bardiya	6	10-25
Kailali	4	26-25
Kanchanpur	12	>50
Palpa	2	26-50
Syanja	3	10-25
Kaski	3	26-50
Tanahu	5	>50
Gorkha	1	<10
Kathmandu	5	>50
Bhaktapur	6	10-25
Lalitpur	4	10-25
Nuwakot	5	<10
Kabhre	4	10-25
Sindhuli	5	10-25
Total	170	

Terai districts Jhapa, Morang, Bara, Parsa, and Kanchanpur had the highest BB infection (Table 1). In the hills, Tanahu and Kathmandu districts had the highest.